

Consciousness: The Phenomenon of Being - Part 3: A Dimensional Approach to Phenomenal Experience

What is Reality? Experiences or a Physical Universe?

Reality at its core is not made up of “space”, “time” or even a physical universe but rather only “moments”. This is to say that from the perspective of every existing observer, there are only “moments” that exist. Sure such moments are experienced as strung together in order to make up broader “events” that seemingly happen in a “real” physical universe. However all any observer could be sure of is that these “moments” are real and not the physical universe. Of course, within these combined sequences of moments there does seem to be a semblance of existing as a physical being living inside a physical world, however it is important to keep in mind that experientially that physical world is never as fundamental to any observer as the “moments” are. For it is the “moments” that make up ones reality and not space or the physical universe.

This should not be a controversial idea in any right as the only means in which any physical universe is ever experienced is through the lens of stringed together moments from the perspectives of observers. Sure these “moments” can be reduced to physiological mechanisms, however reduction to these mechanisms does not de-fundamentalize these moments as the basic units of “realizing” reality.

An Argument Against “Anthropocentric” Biases

The argument against this view would be that “moments” and experiences are a product of biological beings and therefore aren’t fundamental to the “reality” of everything that exists but rather only seem fundamental from the perspectives of living beings. This argument would state that any ontic claim of “experienced moments” being fundamental, frames reality as anthropocentric meaning that its mechanics are biased to only account for human experience and not everything else. However, since the only means by which anyone knows that there is a “reality” in the first place is through observation and therefore experience, I would argue that an anthropocentric theory of reality isn’t “biased” in any way but rather completely in line with a world that is only ever known to be experienced through the observations of beings. For the universe in which we seem to reside in likes to trick us into believing that what we observe is more real than ourselves observing it. However from the perspective of every observer, there is only a “mind” that is lived in to which the physical universe is secondary. Sure the contents of such a “mind” can be rationalized through the biology of a brain, but the actual crux of “experience” in of itself as being fundamental cannot be denied no matter the mechanisms utilized to “make sense” of them.

Can Brains Alone Explain the Subjective Underlinings of Processed Experience?

Now moments themselves are generally presumed to be processes of a physical “biological brain” subject to the passage of time. While on a physiological level, the brain perhaps is responsible for filling the contents of moments with perceptions of the physical universe and using memory as means to string these moments together, that does not actually explain why there needs to be

any sense of a “subjective experience” at all that underlies these moments. Sure the physiological activity of brains could account for the “content” of moments but cannot explain the contexts of moments and what actually underlies processes of the brain to be subjectively experienced.

To elaborate, the mechanisms of experience could be explained objectively by neural mechanisms. However, the fact that there is a very real subjective underlining to these mechanisms cannot be. For if “moments” are simply the result of “processes”, then at what point do these processes actually become experienced by a subjective observer?

Furthermore, why does one subjective being exist as only able to view reality from the perspective of one set of neural mechanisms and one specific brain? What is it that separates this individual realm of experience from the rest of the objective universe in the first place? Why does there exist *separate* subjective underlinings of awareness in the first place and why do these subjective underlinings act as separate entities on their own and not simply as combined with the entire objective “whole” universe? If the universe as a whole is simply a giant “block” of objective content with some components that have mechanisms for experience then why are these components able to exist as experiencing separated processes from the rest of the objective whole in the first place? Why do these separated “experiencers” experience the products of their mechanisms on their own and why doesn’t the entirety of the universe simply experience the combination of all of its mechanisms together?

The key question here is this - what is it that contextualizes the “objective block of everything that exists” into different things that can individually “utilize” experiential mechanisms in order to have experiences? It is not enough to merely state that brains are machines that develop “experience” since there is nothing then to explain why there is ever a subjectivity that underlies such experiences and why one beings processes that result in subjective experience are separate from the processes of the rest of the universes.

The “Mind” and “Space”

This subjective underling of experience or “the mind” in this way could be likened to space. Space is littered with quantum fields that fluctuate and become excited in order to create the illusion of “particles” that act as the basis for ever single thing inside of the universe. However, these quantum fields are not actually the same as space but rather exist *INSIDE* of space. The actual realm of space in which they exist is something else entirely. Furthermore, even theories that seek to quantize space itself and define it (such as Loop Quantum gravity) still require a “realm” for “quantized space” to exist within. This is to say that no matter how encompassing any system of quantized space may be, it must also itself exist within somewhere. For example, even if such an all “encompassing” space can be conceived of mathematically as Hilbert Space (a mathematical space that consists of quantum wave functions), there still must be an overarching “realm” for that Hilbert space to supposedly exist within. This ultimately leads to an infinite loop of “containers” within “containers” where it would be impossible to ever conceive of an “all-encompassing” space or “container” since every such container must also itself have a container.

Just as space contains “physical content”, the mind contains “experiences”. These experiences consist of the products of neurochemical excitations executed by the brain. The sensations, perceptions and thoughts essentially build these “experiences” that fill the “mind space” just as how quantum fields fill physical space. However the actual container of the mind itself is not accounted for by such neural impulses. This mind “space” is rather only a subjective container inside of which the information garnered by the brain’s processes exist. This “space” of the mind is a subjective “container” that presumedly is a separated realm from all of the other “realms” in the universe. It is a container where the information of a brain’s processes are “realized” and exist within it. Just as how there is a “container problem” when it comes to discovering the nature of “physical space” so too the same is true of “mind space”.

Perhaps this “container problem” exposes a fundamental flaw of reductionism. Reductionism is a scientific means of defining “the nature of something” by its reducible components. However, reducing entities to their most fundamental components does not actually describe how these entities can exist within “anywhere”. After all, anything that exists must also fundamentally exist within “somewhere” - whether that somewhere be a physical space or a mind. Any entity could therefore be described by its components but without an “area” for it to exist within such an entity couldn’t be said to properly exist. Therefore, while reductionism is successful in determining the nature of “content” and the objective nature of things, it at the same time neglects context and the “subjective” nature of things.

The Objective Contents of the Physical Universe

Objectively, the contents of the physical universe should not be described as “materials” or “particles” but rather as “information”. This is because it is only through the subjective viewpoints of observers that the information associated with the contents of the physical universe are understood and categorized as “materials” and “particles”. In reality, particles (or fluctuations of quantum fields) themselves are simply just iotas with “certain properties” that are only meaningful when interacting with other iotas that also have “certain properties”. These properties such as the polarization of a photon or angular spin of an electron are just “informational bits” used to describe independent entities. Therefore, objectively a particle itself is just “information” describing a specific combination of properties and states.

The Dichotomy of What and Where

From here, a dichotomy between the reducible “information” iotas that make up everything physical and the encompassing space that contains them could be established. For if every physical particle or “informational iota” in the physical universe exists at a certain position in spacetime, then such a “spacetime” would not be associated with the “what” of a particle but rather with the “where” of a particle.

Furthermore, if reality itself is composed of experiences, then the “information” (or particles) embedded in spacetime can be described as not only the “contents” of spacetime but also as the contents of experiences. Since essentially any “information” that exists in the universe does not only exist within certain coordinates of space and time but can also exist within the experiences

of “subjective experiencers” or *minds*, such minds must be accounted for when talking about the “where” of information.

Again this is because the processes of the brain alone are not sufficient in describing a “subjective underlining of experience” or *mind* since the brain itself is just information and cannot account for the subjective place where the information it processes is independently experienced. Therefore, just as “information” such as particles require a “spacetime” to exist in, they also require a “subjective context” or *mind* to exist in.

This should not be confused with the idea that “thoughts” and awareness in any way exist independently from the information of the physical universe. After all, “thoughts” and “feelings” are themselves just functions of the brain which is itself just information within the physical universe and composed of particles. The subjective context or *mind* here is not related to the actual contents of thoughts and feelings, but rather acts as the “where” in which those thoughts, feelings and experiences are experienced. It therefore makes sense that this “where” must be accounted for when talking about the “locations” of particles just as the other dimensions of spacetime are. This is to say that the subjective context in this regard is a passive participant in the process of experience just as the other dimensions of spacetime are. It is simply a “location” in which the products of the brains processing capabilities are situated.

How Experiences themselves are Formulated

If experiences themselves are “locations” in which information can exist, then it is important to describe the process of how such experiences come about.

Through the mechanisms of a brain an observer is able to intake information from its surrounding environment and process it into “perceptions” and the contents of experiences.

Take the example of the perception of a tree. A tree in reality is not actually a tree. Instead what is known as a “tree” is just a series of informational inputs into the brain that are schematized and translated as a “tree”. The tree in reality is just information that the brain inputs from its surroundings and translates as having the properties of what it has named a “tree”. The actual source informational input that is associated with the tree is actually unknowable. This is because the brain filters its’ surrounding information in a manner that is evolutionary productive and not based on what best represents the informations objective existence. For this reason, the evolutionarily refined filters of the brain essentially “block” observers from seeing the information at it actually exists and instead makes them see a highly filtered alteration.

This information that is associated with a “tree” is also translated as existing at a certain position within the “world of experience” that the observer observes. This “world of experience” is what the observer comes to know as “the physical universe”. For the observer topologically maps the series of input information taken into his or her brain and then constructs an internal “world of experience” that allows them to exist. The different informational iotas inside of this “world of experience” are then translated as being located in different coordinates of spacetime only in order to make sense of how any one piece of information is separated from another. For this reason, the spacetime that is observed is just an estimation of the spacetime that actually exists

as home to the informational input. It is a manufactured realm where translated information exists as separate from one another. The actual “dimensions” in which the informational inputs can only therefore be mathematically defined. Finally, all of the information along with the topological “world of experience” (space time) that the information itself resides in, is ultimately “experienced” within the subjective context or *mind* of an experienter.

From here it can be seen that in order for the subjective conception of a “tree” to exist it must live inside not only a “physical spacetime” but also a “subjective contextual space” or a mind. For anything that does not live inside a “contextual space” can’t exist subjectively since it can only be objectively known as “information”. Only once this information enters the “mind” of an observer can it be given a subjective existence since it is this “dimension” of observers that allows subjectivity to come into play in the first place. For without a “mind” to live in, the tree is not a tree but just “information” that can only be looked at objectively one way.

Minds as Dimensional Coordinates

If the 4 dimensions of spacetime can be conceived of by different observers, then it makes sense that different observers could relate to them in similar manners and provide them similar properties (such as objective measures of time and distance).

However, just as space and time in this way are considered dimensions, so too “subjective contexts” or *minds* could be considered “dimensional” as well. This is because “information” that exists in 4d spacetime also exists within the “experiences” of subjective observers.

Once accepting that there is a distinction to be made between the “neuronal mechanisms” that allow for observation and the subjective context that underlies them, then not only would “information” need to be present in the 4 dimensions of spacetime but also in an added dimension of “subjective context” or experience. This 5th dimension would not be a spatial dimension or a temporal dimension but a 3rd dimensional class known as an “experiential dimension”.

Describing Limitations of Dimensional Complexity

If one wanted to meet their friend at a certain location they’d need to provide them with 4 pieces of information: the latitude, longitude, altitude and time at which they were to meet. For example, if a man named Bob wanted to meet his friend John at a certain restaurant, Bob would need to tell John the 3d location of the restaurant (its latitude, longitude, altitude) and also the time at which he’d like to meet (perhaps 12 PM on Monday). As these 4 pieces of information sufficiently describe the “realm” in which entities such as John and Bob reside, it is presumed that these 4 dimensions are sufficient in describing a classical view of the physical universe. For on the surface level it seems as though these 4 “informational degrees of freedom” (3 spatial and 1 temporal) are what provide a “realm” for entities to exist and interact in.

However, note that these 4 pieces of information used to describe the “dimensionality” of the physical universe are only from the perspective of subjective observers who seem to reside in these 4 dimensions. They therefore do not objectively describe the “informational degrees of

freedom” of the universe but rather only those dimensions that are “conceivable” by subjective entities within it.

For a moment, assume that each coordinate of length (1 of the 3 spatial dimensions) are themselves capable of experience and movement through the other 3 spatial and time dimensions. Now say that one coordinate of length (longitude 70) wanted to meet another coordinate of length (longitude 30) at certain points in (width, altitude, time). The first coordinate of length would need to provide the second coordinate of length with the width, altitude and time coordinates in order to meet.

Now obviously, one could say that the 2 coordinates of longitude themselves could never actually be “near” one another in this case since they wouldn’t be at similar positions in length. Since our conception of spacetime includes the dimension of length we intuitively require it as a necessity of proximity. Therefore it is natural for us to think that if 2 entities are separated in the dimension of length, they can’t be in proximity to one another in terms of their “positional spatial location”.

However, perhaps this is a biased view of dimensionality present from the experiential constraints of beings who themselves exist within 4 spatial/temporal dimensions. Perhaps from the perspectives of the 2 length coordinates themselves, they would never actually have a conception of the dimension of length (since they themselves are always embedded to the same “coordinate” in that dimension). For if they are only ever on the same coordinates in the length dimension they would never notice any other “coordinates” within that dimension and wouldn’t be able to have a conception of the dimension of length in the first place. This is obviously because they wouldn’t notice what is constant and unchanging (the axis of length on which they exist as coordinates).

Therefore, they could meet at the other 3 coordinates of spacetime, since from their perspective those are the three dimensions they are capable of conceiving of, since they themselves cannot conceive of the dimensions of length. To them, the other 3 coordinates of spacetime define the “realm” in which they live in that is movable and traversable. The dimension of length to them would not be traversable to them since they are always stuck to the same coordinate within it and therefore do not notice it (since they are the coordinates). For this reason, to the 2 coordinates of length, proximity is not defined by L,W,H,T but only W,H,T. This is not to say that “coordinates of length” are themselves conscious entities capable of movement and meeting one another but rather is just to meant to illustrate how coordinates of a dimension do not “notice” the dimension they themselves are a part of.

Describing Experiential Dimensions

It can be said that perhaps “subjective contexts” or observers themselves are incapable of noticing a “5th dimension” only because they themselves are coordinates in it. For just as the 2 coordinates of length do not notice the dimension of length since they are always at the same point within it, so too the two observers would not notice the dimension of “observers” since they themselves are points within it. Furthermore, if the 2 observers themselves are embedded to the same points in the “experiential 5th dimension” they wouldn’t be able to notice any other

points in the dimension and would it take it for granted that only their dimensional coordinate exists. Perhaps this is why there can never be a true “movement” in subjective consciousness between 2 entities since they themselves are the coordinates in the “dimension of experience” and therefore could not conceive of the other coordinates in that dimension let alone “traverse” them. For since ones coordinate in the “dimension of experience” is embedded to their individual brain, so too they could never experience “conscious experience” through the processes of any other physical entity. This means to say that they can’t shift consciousness because the consciousness is what they are and obviously something can’t shift what it essentially is.

This suggests that perhaps there are really 5 pieces of information Bob and John need to “truly” be one another. However, since because Bob and John are always themselves “tied” to the same coordinate in the “experiential dimension” they themselves do not notice that dimension and it is irrelevant for them to specify it (since coordinates themselves cannot move within the dimension in which they are themselves coordinates). They therefore are always separated in that dimension of experience since they are coordinates within that dimension. For this reason, Bob and John could never truly “experience” each others experiences since they are always separated within the “dimension of experience”.

This 5th dimension of experience would describe the degrees of freedom of the physical universe just as the 3 spatial dimensions and 1 temporal dimensions do. In fact, it could be said that this “dimension of experience” allows for subjectivity itself to exist as subjectivity comes about when “information” is looked at in different contexts. Without a dimension of “observers” there would be nothing underlying the perception and judgment of information and therefore no way to ever contextualize it or make it subjective.

What it Means

This idea of a “dimension of experience” is not meant to suggest that there are “5 physical dimensions” - length, width, height, time and experience. After all, “dimensions” themselves are just a human conception used to understand the degrees of freedom associated with the universe. It is rather meant to show how “the realm of subjective experience” truly is a fundamental degree of freedom similar to space and time that requires a real physical explanation.

For the physical universe is generally thought of as a 4 dimensional block with “quantum fields” within it, when in reality “the realm of experience” is a fundamental part of it that is not generally taken into account when talking about the “physical nature of the universe”. Thinking of the subjective underlinings as coordinates within a “dimension of experience” is helpful in terms of acknowledging the “realm of subjective experience” as a real part of the physical universe. While it is not intuitive to think of the realm of experience as “a degree of freedom of the physical universe” this is only because to each individual observer, their position in this dimension is always constant which means they would never notice the dimension itself and cant conceive of differences within in.

Perhaps the real lesson here is that the subjective “mind” is a real degree of freedom that needs to be researched as not either a strictly material phenomenon within the dimensions of spacetime nor a metaphysical phenomenon. It should rather be researched as a physical phenomenon; albeit one that is not properly understood or accounted for in current physical models of the universe.